

MIT ART, DESIGN AND TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY
MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

7th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
RECENT TRENDS IN BIOENGINEERING
(ICRTB 2024)

January 19-20, 2024

ABSTRACTS

MIT School of
**Bioengineering Sciences
& Research**

Breathe Life into Engineering Career!

MIT-ADT
UNIVERSITY
PUNE, INDIA

A Leap Towards The World Class Education

OP-016

Constructing comprehensive Omic database for Parkinson's disease in Indian subpopulation

Jitendra Rajput, Shweta Tiwari, Dhruv Ramgire

Department of Biotechnology, Sinhgad College of Engineering, Pune, Maharashtra

Abstract: Parkinson's disease represents a chronic and progressive neurological ailment that predominantly has an impact on the central nervous system. In industrialized nations, its prevalence is approximated at 0.3% across the general population and notably escalates to 3% among individuals aged 65 and above. A comprehensive analysis of the literature suggests that the epidemiological profile of Parkinson's disease in India may differ. Notably, many of the genetic mutations implicated in PD among other populations do not appear to be prevalent in the Indian context. So we are constructing appropriate database classifying the genetic data, SNPs, and drug interactions. It would greatly aid in understanding on PD which in turn can provide new insights in the control and treatment of PD. We have collected genetic data from different biological databases available (GenBank, PubMed). This data includes gene name, gene ID, FASTA sequence, also identifying mutations that result in Parkinson's disease phenotypes. The PD database catered to Indian population will help in scientific consensus among researchers and will foster research in the field. This work presents the development of a comprehensive genetic database for Parkinson's disease specific to the Indian sub-population.

Keywords: Parkinson's disease, genetic database, Indian sub-population, comprehensive

MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

Bioengineering is a multidisciplinary field that has gained immense importance in the global scenario. MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research is a constituent unit of MIT Art, Design and Technology University that aims to prepare students for ambitious careers in bioengineering by imparting education and hands-on training through project-based learning. The school helps in introducing students to the world of untapped opportunities in biology using engineering skills. The school envisions to empower India to become a leader in Bioengineering research, development and manufacturing sectors. It offers B. Tech. (Bioengineering), Int. M. Tech. (Bioengineering), M. Tech. (Environmental Bioengineering), M.Sc (Industrial Biotechnology) and Ph.D Programs in Biotechnology, Biomedical Engineering, Bioinformatics and Biomaterials. The super-specialized courses include Pharmaceutical Engineering, Synthetic Biology, Big Data Analytics, Biosensors and IoT, Biomedical Imaging, Biomechanics, Nano-Biotechnology, Robotics, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, Environmental bioengineering, etc. The school is equipped with state-of-art laboratories for carrying out high-end research and innovative product development.

Rajbaug, Next to Hadapsar, Loni Kalbhor, Pune 412201, India.

+91 744 7444 027 / 28 | +91 914 6051 841 / 42

[www.mitbio.edu.in / icrtb](http://www.mitbio.edu.in/icrtb) | Email: icrtb@mituniversity.edu.in

ISBN 978-93-6039-051-8

